

Download & Setup Overhead

Overhead is a rough prototype at the moment and a bit tricky to use. To make it work, you'll also need [OBS](#) (which is free) or a similar software that can generate a virtual webcam. *Overhead* is made for MacOS only at the moment.

The prototype setup is this: The tool outputs a transparent overlay with its contents (like text and drawing). You need an extra tool like OBS to take your actual webcam feed and combine it with the overlay. OBS can then output this composition as a virtual webcam you can select in any video platform.

(*Overhead* could also show the webcam feed itself to remove some setup steps, but this results in a way less fluid video stream at the moment.)

Steps to set up *Overhead*

1. Download the [Overhead application here](#) (~240 MB) and unzip it.
2. Download [OBS here](#) (free and open source) and install it.
3. Start *Overhead*. This is a bit tricky:

The app by itself is not allowed to access your webcam (it uses the webcam for the preview in the app). When you just open the *Overhead* app, it should crash. You need to start it via your Terminal to have the necessary permissions. One way to do it is to create a link to the executable file that is packed up inside the `Overhead.app` file:

1. Right-click on the `Overhead.app` and choose *Show Contents*.
2. Open the *Contents* folder.
3. Open the *MacOS* folder.
4. Create an Alias (a shortcut link) to the executable file *Overhead* in that folder. Either by right-clicking on the file and choosing *Make Alias* or by holding `CMD+Option` while dragging the file. You can move the alias to wherever you want to start *Overhead* from (like the Desktop or your Applications folder).
5. Double-click the Alias to start *Overhead*. This will open a Terminal window that opens the application (if you close the Terminal window, the app will close as well).

4. The application window should pop up and show a video image and the *Overhead* interface.

By default, the tool tries to find your *FaceTime* camera and display it. With `CMD+C` you can switch through the available camera inputs.

5. Start OBS.
6. Setup OBS:

In OBS, you need to set up a scene with two layers: the webcam you want to overlay and the output of *Overhead*. *Overhead* outputs a *Syphon* stream, which is a video signal that OBS can use as a video source. Here is how you set up your scene:

1. Create a new scene in the *Scenes* panel in OBS.
2. In the *Sources* panel, first create a layer with a *Video Capture Device*. In the settings, choose the webcam you want to overlay.
3. Scale the webcam image to fit the stage (right click the webcam image preview → *Transform* → *Fit to Screen*).
4. In the *Sources* panel, create a second source layer of the type *Syphon Client*. When *Overhead* is running, you should be able to select its *Syphon* stream in the settings of the layer. Also select *Allow Transparency* in the settings.
5. Scale the layer to fit the stage (right click the layer in the preview → *Transform* → *Fit to Screen*). Make sure it is above the webcam layer.
6. If you type text into the *Overhead* app window now, it should be visible in OBS.

7. In OBS, select *Start Virtual Camera* from the *Controls* panel.

8. Now you can choose OBS as your webcam in any video meeting platform. It will show the selected scene in OBS as your webcam image.

The settings in OBS are usually preserved when you quit the program. You can also save the OBS scene setup.

Anytime you want to use *Overhead*, you would:

1. Open *Overhead* via the alias link
2. Open OBS
3. Choose your OBS scene
4. Start the OBS virtual webcam
5. Select OBS as your webcam.

The whole setup is not super performant, so your CPU might run high while using *Overhead*.

Easy-peasy ;)

And in case you really got that far, here is how to use the thing.

Controls in *Overhead*

There are not many on-screen controls in the tool and most things are accessed with keyboard shortcuts to keep the tool compact and handy (okay, I had no time yet to make a decent user interface...).

The yellow rectangle indicates the text position and size. The yellow circle is the drawing cursor in the brush size.

The app window switches appearance when it is not active or in focus (so you better see if it's reacting to input). The window can't be resized at the moment.

Text

- `Type` directly in the tool window to write. Line breaks work.
- `Backspace` to delete single characters.
- `CMD+Backspace` to delete the whole text.
- `Left/Right` keys to change text size.
- `CMD+0...6` to change text position
- `CMD+V` to paste text from the clipboard. Text is added to the existing text.

Drawing

- `Scroll` to change brush size.
- `Click+Drag` to draw.
- `CMD+X` to delete the drawing.

Colors

- `Hold Shift + move mouse` to show color picker for brush.
- `Hold Shift + Alt + move mouse` to show color picker for text.
- `Scroll` while in the color picker to adjust saturation.

Images

- `CMD+V` to paste an image file or copied image from a website or elsewhere.
- `CMD+I` to toggle image display.
- Transparent images work.

Video

- `CMD+C` to switch through available camera inputs for preview.
- `CMD+B` to blur the video.
- `CMD+M` to overlay a circle mask.
- `CMD+D` to disable or block the video.

Window

- `CMD+T` to keep the *Overhead* app on top of other windows.